

POWER HEGEMONY: MARITIME ORGANIZATIONAL TRANSFORMATION DIALECTICS ON POLITEKNIK MARITIM NEGERI, INDONESIA

Sri Tutie Rahayu¹

Department Port and Shipping Management,
Politeknik Maritim Negeri Indonesia,
Semarang, Indonesia

Abstract:

The purposes of this research are: 1) Describe the organizational transformation process of SGC into Polimarin; 2) Describe the dialectic (process) that occurs during the SGC transformation process into Polimarin. The type of this research is qualitative case study with single case (single case single analysis). Four themes in the analysis: Theme 1 "preparing the land", theme 2 "finding the seed", theme 3 "waiting for planting season", theme 4 "planting and bloom though cannot be harvested yet". Existing institutional actors in the four themes are the main actors in Polimarin, Directorate General of Higher Education, Directorate General of Sea Transportation and IMO (International Maritime Organization).

Keywords: organizational transformation, planned change organization, continuity transformation, international competency integration, hegemonic

1. Introduction

In the early 1980s (Kural & Kocakulah, 2016), one of the most striking conceptual explanations of Change was made by Posner, Strike, (Hewson, 1981) with Conceptual Theory of Change based on Scientific Revolution Theories (Kuhn, 1970). Trying to survive in an ever-changing environment is not an easy thing because it's hard to identify the signs of change. Organizational change seems to be the real need of

¹ Correspondence: email tutie@polimarin.ac.id

organizations in facing increasingly fierce competition. Organizational adaptability is now become a concern.

Initially, the idea of establishing Semarang Growth Center (SGC) was aimed at helping private universities, especially in Kopertis VI Region of Central Java by providing facilities and infrastructure for helping the implementation of the learning process.

In a relatively long time, about 20 years, there has been an organizational change (SGC - BPLPT - Polimarin). Initially the scope of SGC was locally in Central Java. In the end, after becoming BPLPT and Polimarin, the institution operates and simultaneously collaborates with various domestic and foreign stakeholders, such as World Maritime University (WMU) Sweden as one of the foreign stakeholders, a leading maritime university in the world established by IMO (International Maritime Organization) based in England, also the University of Warnemunde, based in Rostock, Germany.

Darwin on *survival of the fittest* and *Blancard the key to successful leadership is influence not authority*, among the arguments of the importance of institutional change or *change* (Kasali, 2005). Changes in organizational performance become increasingly clear, binding between what is done and the result, more energy, commitment, and passion that will be generated during the change process (Kotler & Armstrong, 1996), (Passmore, 1994).

Change is used to distinguish between episodic, non-continuous, and intermittent changes with continuous, evolving change. This distinction is central to the conceptualization of organizational change so that when viewed from the viewer's perspective, a more detailed analysis and comparison between the episodic and continuous changes develops into a framework proposed by (Weick & Quinn, 1999), the change lies in the practice not from something initiated by management (Orlikowski, 1996), and the result of continuous updates to routines (Levit & March, 1998) and on work processes (Brown & Duguid, 2000).

Leadership dynamics color the long journey of SGC. Resistance on the existence of SGC with maritime polytechnics "owned" by the Directorate General of Sea Transportation, Ministry of Transportation can be a potential conflict; there is the impression that SGC "seize" maritime education area. The three groups may at least be referred to as near-research objects or variables; Firstly, the struggle between policies and interests of action-reaction-interaction between leading actors that play in the long journey of the institution; second, the institution's activities or programs in handling the training, research services, and education for the expanding students; Third, the appreciation of individual employees-lecturers in the process of adjustment-call it a

kind of compromise process. This transformation process can go on and on, reach the "peak", as in this study.

2. Material and Methods

This study uses a qualitative approach; qualitative approaches emphasize more to the meaning of the things observed. Since the organization is very complicated, it can be used as an approach and includes a combined approach between quantitative and qualitative. A number of qualitative research characteristics are mentioned in (Gibson, Ivancevich, & Donnelly, 1989).

Experts such as (Yin, 1994), (Cresswel, 2013), (Van & Khan, 2007), and Lincoln and (Guba & Lincoln, 1988), say that case study research may use theory. Furthermore, Van Wynsberghe and Khan (2007) argue that case study research is unique, which is not merely a research method or research design, but case study research as transparadigmatic heuristics and transdisciplinary in describing in detail the evidence such as events, concepts, processes and programs.

The transformation process proposed by (Gouillart & Kelly, 1995) states that change occurs through the involvement of mind, body of institution, environment that surround the institution and spirit, further the institution will move forward to follow the changes with adjustments to the main things (revitalize), on the organizational structure (restructure), on the framework of institutions (reframe) and renewal as an action of changes in various places within the organization (renew).

Critical theory comes from Hegel and Marx. The development of this theory begins with Karl's conviction of the idea of modernity in terms of reason and freedom. There are four western philosophers who developed the critical theory of Socrates, Kant, Marx and Hegel (Faitanu, 2012: 245). Socrates posed a way of thinking that begins with a question about the problems that arise. Kant (Faitanu, 2012: 268-274) develops critical

thinking with Kant's theory of imperative categorical, that is a necessity in the human being associated with certain metaphysical ideas, since man sees an unreal phenomenon - from the reality of the object (Kant noumena) which is a form of noumena that has been influenced by space and time and depends on the perception of each. Hegel then criticized Kant's thinking. He argues that Kant's critical ratio is timeless, neutral and ahistorical. According to him, the ratio becomes critical if the former is known and will be critical if there are obstacles. This process is called the dialectical model. A process of finding solutions in the presence of contradictions between elements. According to Hegel's critical ratio is the ratio that has been through the barriers during its formation.

Change and Transformation are words that are often used in something related to change. Joan argues that fundamentally, transformation has changed a form both internally and externally. The conclusion is that transformation is a process of change whereas resocialization is the key in sustaining behavioral change.

The concepts of Gouillar J.F and Kelly N.J. (1995) in "*Transforming the Organization*" that the organization is compared to the human body that needs treatment. So the concept proposed is to see transformation as a whole process with approaches: *reframing, restructure, revitalize, and renewal*.

The emergence of other genre that provide a new paradigm in the critical theory, it is the Frankfurt genre with its figures Adorno and Habermas. In general, it can be concluded that critical theory is a theory to do explanation about the existence of the condition that is considered false or not true and provide enlightenment, human emancipation so that social actors are aware of hidden coercion (hegemony). (Saudah in Bagung Suyanto, 2013: 271).

Hegel's dialectics are triadic in form of thesis-antithesis-synthesis. This dialectic comes from dialogue in daily communication. (Suyanto, 2013: 73). From the phenomenon of dialogue can be seen three stages of thesis, antithesis and synthesis. The thesis is a preliminary and antithesis opinion of being the opposite or opposition to the thesis. While synthesis is the reconciliation between from thesis and the antithesis. In this synthesis there is annihilation and annulment either from thesis or antithesis. In Hegel's view, this process is called *aufgehoben*.

The purpose of dialectics is to learn things in Hegel, the element of contradiction (antithesis) does not appear after we reflected it but the contradictions already exist in the case itself. Each thesis already contains the antithesis in it. Both are removed and annihilated (*aufgehoben*) in Synthesis The point Hegel asserts is that contradictions are inherently internal in many respects. Hegel has laid down that them themselves. One important principle for Hegel's dialectics is the change from quantity to quality.

Karl Marx and Friedrich Engels believed Hegel "stood on his head" and attempted to reestablish himself, cleansing Hegel's logic toward philosophical idealism and containing what is now known as materialist or Marxis dialectics. Engels argues that the whole universe is dialectic. Hegel's dialectics is developed from Kant's philosophy; Hegel's dialectics then reduces and develops his own characteristics.

This study still makes an empirical fact as a source of knowledge so this study is a qualitative research by reviewing the behavior performed by humans ranging from way of thinking to how to act. This study is a qualitative research with a case and single analysis (*single case single analysis*) so it is called a non-positivistic paradigm because it builds direct knowledge from its source.

The steps in this case study are preparing an instrument of in-depth interviews and focused group discussion (FGD), collecting primary and secondary data, performing data processing, analyzing and interpreting data, summarizing and making recommendations.

Researchers set one institution that became the focus of research, which is Semarang Growth Center (SGC). While the element being studied is the organizational transformation that occurs in SGC by looking at the dialectic that occurs in the transformation process.

(Stake, 1995) data analysis in case studies is looking for correspondence and patterns, *aggregating* frequencies and finding the pattern. Patterns and correspondence that are looked for and wanted to be interpreted is the transformation of the organization at the SGC. The purpose of the analysis is to find a theme that shows the orderliness of the organization's transformation management in SGC.

Trustworthiness in this study lies in reliability and validity. In this study, reliability is done by evaluating the data collection procedure, whether the method has been interpreted and produce the desired data. Validity in this study used triangulation of data sources, data collection and theory.

3. Results and Discussion

The transformation begins with a critical phenomenon with a conflict of interest in the leadership box, the dialectic that occurs in the transformation process of BPLPT into Polimarin is "Planned Transformation Change".

Transforming The Organization of Guillart and Kelly (1995), there are four variables that are then broken down into 12 sub-sets of indicators; they are reframing, restructuring, revitalize and renewal. The process of changing Polimarin when

consulted on the frame transformation process presented by Guillard and Kelly known as 4 R's.

Identification and analysis of Polimarin's Internal Issues, related to "conflicts" that occur among personnel (leaders, lecturers, staffs/employee).

External Conflict / Macro Analysis Two Departments or Ministries (Directorate General of Higher Education – Ministry of Education and Culture and Directorate General of Sea Transportation – Ministry of Transportation).

External conflicts experienced by Polimarin can be seen in the following figure:

4. Findings

Three Characteristics of Organizational Transformation have been discovered:

- a. The *Unplanned Change* Transformation becomes *Planned Change*.
- b. The *Continuity* Transformation From the Beginning until Now
- c. *Unintegration* into *Integration*.

5. Scope of the Broadness Integration Process

POLIMARIN	
1. Actor	Directorate General of Higher Education and the Head of BPLPT
2. Mechanism	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Planning: Initial planning to be BPLPT as a new institution established by the Regulation of the Minister of National Education No. 13 year 2011 and the Principal was assigned to create a work program immediately 2. Implementation: The work program was realized by the preparation of BPLPT development proposal further into a State Maritime Polytechnic 3. Evaluation: The development of BPLPT into Polimarin was evaluated positively and realized the completion of the proposed changes along with all the completeness documents
3. Process	BPLPT as a new institution, substitute the SGC, with the status as a new state technical implementation unit under the Directorate General of Higher Education as one of its Work Unit, further in its work program proposed the development of BPLPT into a Polytechnic and immediately processed its institution through Legal and Organization Bureau, Ministry of National Education and immediately proposed to the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform
4. Impact	The result was the approval of the Minister of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform to change the form or transformation of BPLPT into a Polytechnic under the name of Indonesia State Maritime Polytechnic (Polimarin) the only Maritime Education under the control of Directorate General of Higher Education, Ministry of Education and Culture.

Directorate General Of Higher Education	
1. Actor	Directorate General of Higher Education
2. Mechanism	Setting up consultations with the Ministry of Education and having the authority of the command line to Polimarin
3. Process	<p>1. Planning: The SGC transformation into a state institution was proposed by the Directorate General of Higher Education to the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform</p> <p>2. Implementation: Preparation of the completeness requirements for the transformation into the state institution was directed by the Directorate of Institutional, Directorate General of Higher Education and Legal and Organization Bureau of, Ministry of National Education</p> <p>3. Evaluation : All went well</p>
4. Impact	Finally, the proposal of SGC certification to BPLPT (Development and Higher Education Service Agency) was permitted by the Ministry of Administrative and Bureaucratic Reform which established by Regulation of the Minister of National Education No.13 / dated March 15, 2011 by inaugurating Dra. Sri Tutie Rahayu, Msi as the Head of BPLPT on December 2, 2011 by the Minister of National Education in Jakarta, had previously been in charge of SGC since 1993.

Director General of Sea Transportation	
1. Aktor	Director General of Sea Transportation
2. Mechanism	Coordinate with superiors at the Ministry of Transportation Conduct coordination with Polimarin to explore the cooperation opportunities for the equation of the standard marine education curriculum in Indonesia; in accordance with IMO recommendations/standards
3. Process	Coordination with Polimarin is not well established. Particularly with sectoral ego, since the standard IMO training project should be the authority of Director General of Sea Transportation, not Polimarin.
4. Impact	The relationship between Director General of Sea Transportation (Ministry of Transportation) and Polimarin (Ministry of Education and Culture) has not been well established. Further coordination is needed at the central institutional level and the directorate general under it.

International Maritime Organization (IMO)	
1. Actor	President of IMO in London Chairman of Rostock University in Germany
2. Mechanism	Conduct the equipments audit for 11 IMO maritime training certifications, organized by Polimarin, Semarang. The 11 certificates are Basic Safety Training, Survival Craft and Rescue Boats, Medical First Aid, Medical Care,

	<p>Radar Simulator, ARPA Simulator, Crowd Management, Crisis Management, Global Maritime Distress and Safety System, Bridge Team Management, Bridge Resource Management.</p> <p>Provide recommendation of approval that the audit is conducted in Polimarin in accordance to IMO standards</p>
3. Process	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Planning: Audit preparation 2. Implementation of the audit: the team sent the document to be filled. The team went to Polimarin and verified. The team works according to the standards in IMO. 3. The team concludes the audit findings. The team handover proof/certificate to Polimarin.
4. Impact	<p>Because the audit results are standardized (good), then Polimarin still in cooperation to conduct the 11 training.</p> <p>On the other hand, Directorate General of Sea Transportation thinks that Polimarin interferes their business development.</p>

6. Heme and Phase of Transformation and its Analogy

1. The cycle 1 of SGC is to prepare the land for the growth of prospective plants. Occurs in phases 1 and 2; ends with a leadership vacuum.
2. The cycle SGC is to find superior seeds to be planted. Occurs in phase 3, phase 4 and phase 5.
3. The cycle 3 BPLPT/SGC is waiting for the planting period; despite the changing seasons (form changing); occurs in phase 6.
4. The cycle 4 Polimarin/SGC is planting and blooming; although cannot be harvested directly yet; occurs in phases 7 and 8.

7. Dominant/State Hegemonic Role in the Transformation of Indonesian Maritime Training

The four main issues related to the role of state or government hegemony are:

1. The SGC organization is a 'central deposit' (structural);
2. Institutional rules (SGC, BPLPT) from and following the government (juridical, political);
3. Appointment of the leadership of SGC, BPLPT and Polimarin by the government (juridical, political);
4. State revenues are deposited and returned (again) to the state (economical).

8. 4RH's Theory Findings

The proses of *reframe*, *restructure*, *revitalize* and *renewal* is experienced in the transformation of the organization from SGC to BPLPT and Polimarin. However, when the analysis of the various conflicts, pressures, insistence emerge from the transformation process, both internal and external conflicts, involving the interference of the state (read: government) at every step of the solution or problem solving. So it can be said that at the stage of *reframing*, *restructure*, *revitalize* and *renewal*, there is an involvement of state/government hegemony. The new theory found is the interruption of government intervention that cut off the journey from one stage to the next stage in the process of *reframing*, *restructure*, *revitalize* and *renewal*. The following figure shows this new process.

9. Conclusion

1. The 20 years of SGC transformation into Polimarin includes five stages: (a) from a *training center* to the form of the Polytechnic; (b) from a private institution to BPLPT and Maritime Polytechnics as state owned institutions; (c) from a regional scale to a national scale; (d) from a simple structure and business to a complex one; and (e) from a local-level learning organization to a global-level one.
2. The transformation process of Semarang Growth Center into Polimarin is done through eight phases/stages after being established, those are: 1) during the SGC there are six phases; phase 1 "*Forms finding*", phase 2 "*Decline*", phase 3 "*Recovery*", phase 4 "*Cooperation Strengthening*", phase 5 "*Optimum and Leadership Separation*" and phase 6 "*Progressive*" (SGC); 2) during the BPLPT there is one phase that is phase 7 "*Form Exchange*" (BPLPT), and 3) during Polimarin there is one phase that is phase 8 "*Growing*" (Polimarin).
3. The dialectic process has taken place in the transformation of SGC into Polimarin
4. The process of organizational transformation undertaken by SGC-BPLPT-Polimarin has three distinctive features; (1) from *unplanned change* to *planned change*, (2)

continuity, (3) from *unintegration* into *integration*. Integration undertaken by Polimarin is a process of integration of international competence.

10. Theoretical Implications and Practical Implications

1. **Theoretical implications:** this organizational transformation study can be both evidence and enrich the application of effective stages of team development theory (Schermerhorn & Wright, 2007: 25).
2. **Practical Implications;** Polimarin, as a higher education institution currently in form of polytechnic (2014) is considered a final formation, but according to the dialectical law, "New Polymarin" is likely to continue to develop into a more adaptive form.

References

1. Brown, J. S., & Duguid, P. (2000). *Balancing act: How to Capture Knowledge without Killing it*. Harvard Business Review.
2. Cresswel, J. F. (2013). *Penelitian Kualitatif dan Design Riset* (3 ed.). Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar.
3. Fautanu, I. (2012). *Filsafat Ilmu, Teori dan Aplikasi*. Jakarta.
4. Gibson, J. L., Ivancevich, J. M., & Donnelly, J. H. (1989). *Organisasi: Perilaku, Struktur, Proses*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
5. Gouillart, F. J., & Kelly, J. N. (1995). *Transforming the Organization*. New York: Mc Graw-Hill, Inc.
6. Guba, E. G., & Lincoln, Y. S. (1988). Do Inquiry Paradigms Imply Inquiry Methodologies? (D. M. Fatterman, Ed.) *New York: Praeger*, 89-115.
7. Hewson, P. W. (1981). A conceptual Change Approach to Learning Science. *European Journal of Science Education*, 3(4), 383-396.
8. Kasali, R. (2005). *Change*. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka.
9. Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G. (1996). *Prinsip-Prinsip Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
10. Kuhn, T. (1970). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. Chicago: The University of Chicago.
11. Kural, M., & Kocakülah, S. M. (2016). Teaching for Hot Conceptual Change: Towards a New Model, Beyond the Cold and Warm Ones. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 2(8), 2.

12. Levit, B., & March, J. G. (1998). Organizational Learning. *Annual Review of Sociology*, 14, 319-340.
13. Orlikowski, W. (1996). Improvising Organizational Transformation over Time: A Situated Change Perspective. *Information System Research*, 7(1), 63-92.
14. Passmore. (1994). Shaping From Shading I: Surface Curvature And Orientation Vision Research. <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/showciting?cid=2510871>.
15. Schermerhorn, J. R., & Wright, B. (2007). *Management Fundamentals*. Canadian.
16. Stake, R. E. (1995). The art of case study research. *Thousand Oaks, C.A: Sage*.
17. Suyanto, B. (2013). *Filsafat Sosial*. Yogyakarta: Aditya Media.
18. Van, W. R., & Khan, S. (2007). Redefining Case Study. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 6(2).
19. Weick, K. E., & Quinn, R. E. (1999). Organizational Change and Development, *Annual Review of Psychology*. DOI: 10.1146/annurev.psych.50.1.361., 50, 361-386.
20. Yin, R. K. (2005). *Studi Kasus (Design dan Metode)*. Jakarta: PT. Raja Grafindo Persada.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).